

NOTES

Preparation of Optically Active Unsymmetrical Ketones from S-(+)-2-Methyl 1-Cyanobutane

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Optically active unsymmetrical aliphatic ketones of the type, MeCH(Et)-CH₂.CO.R. have been prepared by the Grignard reaction using optically active S-(+)-2-methyl-1-cyanobutane and different alkyl magnesium halides. Treatment of 86% optically pure S-(-)-2-methylbutan-1-ol (I) with bromine and red phosphorus resulted in S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane (II), $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69$ ($l = 1$ dm). It was then treated with potassium cyanide in methanol to obtain desired optically active S-(+)-2-methyl-1-cyanobutane (III), $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.33$ ($l = 1$ dm.). The different Grignard reagents prepared from alkyl halides condensed with S-(+)-2-methyl-1-cyanobutane to yield optically active ketones (IV).

The cyano group is away from the active center and not attached directly to the asymmetric carbon atom, therefore it is not disturbed during the reaction, hence the different alkyl substituted ketones were found to be optically active. The maximum rotation found in case of S-(+)-3, 7-dimethyl-5-octanone, $\alpha_D^{25} + 3.36$ ($l = 1$ dm) and minimum rotation in case of S-(+)-3 : 6-dimethyl-5-octanone, $\alpha_D^{25} + 0.50$ ($l = 1$ dm).

The physical properties including optical activity are recorded in the Table 1.

EXPERIMENTAL

S-(-)-2-Methylbutan-1-ol^{1, 2}: The fusel oil contains one of the constituents as optically active S-(-)-2-methylbutan-1-ol which was obtained by fractional distillation through 16 inch long column, b.p. 126-128°; $\alpha_D^{25} - 4.62$ ($l = 1$ dm); $d_4^{25} 0.8279$; $n_D^{25} 1.450$.

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TABLE I
Optically active unsymmetrical ketones of the type $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\overset{\text{CH}_3}{\text{C}}\text{HCH}_2\text{CO.R}$

Name	R	Yield %	b.p. °C/15 mm	d_D^{25}	Sp. rotation α_D^{25}	n_D^{25}	Mol. Formula	Required C% H%	Found C% H%
1. 3-Methyl-5-hexanone	Methyl	59.0	70-75	0.9557	+3.30	1.414	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$	73.7 11.2	73.6 10.9
2. 3-Methyl-5-heptanone	Ethyl	58.6	80-90	0.9670	+2.36	1.419	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$	75.0 12.5	74.6 12.3
3. 3-Methyl-5-octanone	n-propyl	55.1	104-107	0.9270	+1.04	1.420	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$	76.1 12.7	76.2 12.7
4. 3:6 Dimethyl-5-heptanone	Isopropyl	51.7	*123-125 (25 mm)	0.9364	+2.54	1.458	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$	76.1 12.7	76.0 12.5
5. 3-Methyl-5-nonanone	n-Butyl	60.2	160-170	0.9432	+2.26	1.424	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$	77.3 12.8	77.5 13.0
6. 3:7 Dimethyl-5-octanone	Isobutyl	62.0	70-80	0.9408	+3.36	1.431	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$	77.3 12.8	77.1 12.5
3:6 Dimethyl-5-octanone	sec-Butyl	54.3	85-90	0.9067	+0.50	1.409	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$	77.3 12.8	77.0 12.7
8. 3:6:6 Trimethyl-5-heptanone	tert-Butyl	52.4	140-142	0.9396	+1.83	1.417	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$	77.3 12.8	77.9 12.9
9. 3-Methyl-5-decanone	n-Amyl	62.0	135-137	0.9651	+2.36	1.420	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$	77.7 12.9	77.6 12.7
10. 3-Methyl-5-undecanone	n-Hexyl	60.0	139-140	0.9276	+2.05	1.433	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$	78.3 13.0	77.9 13.0
11. 3-Methyl-5-dodecanone	n-Heptyl	58.2	170-172 (25 mm)	0.9098	+1.44	1.431	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$	78.7 13.1	78.5 12.8
12. 3-Methyl-5-tridecanone	n-Octyl	57.2	108-110	0.9090	+1.21	1.441	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}$	79.3 13.2	79.3 13.5

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane³: It was prepared by bromination of *S*-(-)-2-methylbutan-1-ol (320 g.) with red phosphorus (20.7 g.) and liquid bromine (266.6 g., 86.1 ml). The resulting *S*-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane was obtained at 116-118°. Yield 57.3%. $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69$ ($l = 1$ dm); $d_4^{32} 1.255$; $n_D^{32} 1.455$.

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-cyanobutane⁴: *S*-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane (151 g., 1.0 mole) dissolved in methanol (315 ml) was added to the hot solution of potassium cyanide (66 g., 1 mole) dissolved in water (84 ml). The mixture was refluxed for one and half hour on water-bath. After cooling, the *S*-(+)-2-methyl-1-cyanobutane was extracted with chloroform and then the chloroform was distilled off. The residual crude cyanide was distilled at 125-135° and washed with equal volume of conc. hydrochloric acid, then with water and finally dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The pure *S*-(+)-2-methyl-1-cyanobutane was collected at 128-132°. Yield 87.3%. $\alpha_D^{32} + 1.33$ ($l = 1$ dm); $d_4^{32} 0.9926$; $n_D^{32} 1.420$.

General method for the preparation of S-(+)-2-methylbutan-1-yl alkyl ketone: To the Grignard reagent prepared from the alkyl halide (0.2 mole), dry magnesium (0.2 mole) and ether (100 ml), *S*-(+)-2-methyl-1-cyanobutane (0.2 mole) in ether (40 ml) was added dropwise during 2 hrs. Then the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. and kept overnight. On the next day the Grignard complex was decomposed by 10% ammonium chloride solution (500 ml.). The ketone was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and distilled under vacuum.

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